

Application-based catalytic methanation of steelworks gases under dynamic operating conditions

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a real and application-based scenario for a dynamically driven catalytic methanation unit, using off-gases from an integrated steel mill as input. Several parameters are subject to dynamic changes during the standard production of steel, such as the available amount and composition of the accumulating process gases, the temperature and operating pressure as well as their periodicity. In addition, the available amount of hydrogen can vary depending on the available fluctuating renewable energy for the installed electrolyzer. Analysis of operating parameters and process routes in steelmaking revealed that among many theoretically possible modes of driving a dynamic methanation unit, which are defined in the literature, there is only one realistic application-based scenario. The definition of this case is supported by experiments performed with a three-stage methanation setup in lab-scale. This experimental campaign covered real cases with dynamic flow rates, adjusting the amount of blast furnace and converter gases based on high variations in the availability of hydrogen. It was possible to achieve very stable product gas compositions, even though load changes in gas input power up to 64% in the range of one to 120 min were executed. The dynamic variations did not result in any additional catalyst deactivation through the whole experimental campaign.

1. Introduction

The energy sector and the chemical industry are currently at a critical turning point, as fossil energy carriers are being substituted by renewable energy systems and sustainable energy storage capacities. Every year, the world climate report is published by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change in which the increasing urgency behind a fast and streamlined change towards a renewable energy system is outlined. In this context it is necessary to address every industry sector contributing to the global emissions of greenhouse gases such as carbon dioxide (CO₂) or methane (CH₄). The demand for steel for example is constantly increasing, resulting in a 2019 annual growth rate of 3.6% in global steel production (Uribe-Soto et al., 2017; Hasanbeigi et al., 2016; World Steel Association, 2020). Integrated steelworks satisfy this demand but are consequently major contributors to the global emissions of CO₂ due to the carbon-rich processes involved. The most common route of steel production consists of a blast furnace for the reduction of iron ore, and a converter for the production of molten steel (Remus et al., 2013). During standard operation, by-product gases are created, such as

the blast furnace gas (BFG), basic oxygen furnace gas (BOFG) and coke oven gas (COG). Especially BFG and BOFG are rich in CO₂ as well as carbon monoxide (CO), whereas COG is mainly consisting of hydrogen (H₂) and CH₄ (Table 1) (Remus et al., 2013).

These gases are utilised plant-internally as energy carrier for the power plant as well as auxiliary energy conversion (Medved et al., 2021), but additional energy is required to achieve a thermodynamical optimum of the overall process chain (i3upgrade: Integrated and intelligent upgrade, 2021). This demand is currently satisfied through fossil energy carriers such as natural gas. Considering the targets of the climate agreements and the European Union's green deal, the steel-making sector logically seeks for possibilities to reduce their need for fossil fuels, and their CO₂ emissions consequently. The transition of the current steelmaking route to a sustainable solution was defined as long-term goal for a cleaner production. Instead of using coke as reducing agent, hydrogen produced from water electrolysis or electric arc furnaces, both driven with power from renewables, ought to be integrated. Until then, a bridging technology is required. One promising technology is the synthesis process methanation in which CO₂ and CO react with green hydrogen (H₂) to methane (CH₄) and steam (Equations

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Abbreviations			
<i>The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:</i>			
ΔH_r^0	Reaction enthalpy	COG	Coke oven gas
σ_{H_2}	Ratio of molar hydrogen flow compared to molar flows of CO and CO ₂	GHSV	Gas hourly space velocity
Q_{gas}	Total feed gas volume flow	H ₂	Hydrogen
$V_{catalyst}$	Catalyst volume	H ₂ O	Water or steam
n_i	Molar flows	ID	Inner diameter
x_i	Gas composition	LHV	Lower heating value
W_S	Wobbe-Index	N ₂	Nitrogen
H_S	Higher heating value	Ni	Nickel
BFG	Blast furnace gas	OD	Outer diameter
BFG _{syn}	Synthetic blast furnace gas	PEM	Proton-exchange membrane
BOFG	Basic oxygen furnace gas/converter gas	ppm	Parts per million
CH ₄	Methane	PtX	Power-to-X
C _n H _m	Higher hydrocarbons (C2+)	R1, R2, R3	Reactor 1, 2 or 3
CO	Carbon monoxide	QIR	Gas sampling station
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide	SNG	Synthetic natural gas
		TI	Temperature indicator/measurement point
		vol.-% dry	Share in volume percent (dry basis)
		W1, W2, W3	Heat exchanger 1, 2 or 3

Table 1
Reference values for gas composition of typical by-product gases from an integrated steelworks (Remus et al., 2013).

Parameter	Unit	COG	BFG	BOFG
		Min – Max	Min – Max	Mean
CO ₂	vol.-% dry	1.0–5.4	16.0–26.0	17.2
CO	vol.-% dry	3.4–5.8	19.0–27.0	60.9
H ₂	vol.-% dry	36.1–61.7	1.0–8.0	4.3
N ₂	vol.-% dry	1.5–6.0	44.0–58.0	15.5
CH ₄	vol.-% dry	15.7–27.0	–	0.1
C _n H _m	vol.-% dry	1.4–2.4	–	–

(1) and (2)) (Sabatier and Senderens, 1902).

Equation (3) shows the reaction linking these two highly exothermic reactions (reverse water-gas shift) (Sabatier and Senderens, 1902). The

detailed fundamentals behind methanation in the Power-to-X (PtX) concept, possible reactor designs and available catalysts are documented by Rönisch et al. (2016). The authors also provide an up-to date overview on finished and ongoing projects as well as current state-of-the-art ones. Rosenfeld et al. (2020) addressed the techno-economic and environmental topics of this technology by analysing multiple scenarios for its integration in an integrated steelworks. For the topic of cleaner production also a CO₂ potential impact analysis was performed. The theoretical analysis showed that a case where all fossil fuel based natural gas is substituted with SNG produced by upgrading steel gases through methanation, can result in a CO₂ reduction potential of ~1 MtCO₂/a. The potential for a case where all steel gases (BFG and BOFG) are upgraded was calculated up to 3.8 MtCO₂/a. It shows the high potential of this technology to contribute to an overall cleaner steelmaking process. Furthermore, Goncalves et al. (2019) investigated the behaviour of operational parameters such as biomass content and temperature for a novel concept where the gas mixtures obtained from typical electrolysis are not separated into their compounds but fed into a reactor with liquefied biomass, to obtain syngas containing CH₄ concentrations up to 35 vol.-%.

Especially research on methanation with a focus on dynamic operating conditions evolved into a key topic during the past years. Multiple publications address dynamic, respectively transient operating

Fig. 1. Dynamic parameters and operating modes for methanation synthesis.

parameters, by modelling and simulation as well as through experiments with lab-scaled test reactors, but mainly for pure CO₂ methanation using synthetic gases. Matthischke et al. (2016) carried out an experimental study to evaluate the interaction between a dynamically driven reactor through variations of the inlet volume flow rate, and a recirculation of the product gas stream using fixed-bed CO₂ methanation reactors. An increase in recycle flow affected the results in a positive way, due to the resulting lower fixed-bed temperatures and, consequently, higher CO₂ conversion rates. In terms of dynamics the reactor behaviour was independent of the load change velocity of the volume flow rate ramps executed. Transient effects during dynamic operation of a wall-cooled fixed bed reactor via step changes of the concentrations of H₂ and CO₂ were investigated by Tauer et al. (2019). The authors showed that the overall response time is very short and the rise in the hotspot temperature is smaller compared to steady state operations. Kreitz et al. (2019a) analysed the effect of concentration forcing during the dynamic methanation of CO₂, showing a strong influence of the cycle time and cycle-split ratio on the mean reaction rate. The CH₄ formation rates could be increased when applying high cycling frequencies and a stoichiometric cycle-split ratio, but optimal rates were always achieved with steady state values. Lehner et al. (2017) concluded that for synthesising steelworks gases to methane a load flexible reactor setup is favourable to meet the fluctuations in process gas and hydrogen availability. Hauser et al. (2021) performed steady state and dynamic methanation experiments with synthetic gases from the steelworks industry using a structured reactor with a heat pipe cooling system. They observed that the dynamic variation of syngas power (in the range of 32%) and stoichiometric H₂:CO_x ratio showed no influence in methane conversion compared to the steady state reference experiments. This included different step heights as well as cycle times.

Fig. 1 summarises the possible parameters identified for a dynamic operating mode when running a methanation synthesis. These are transient changes in.

- the total volume flow or catalyst load expressed as gas hourly space velocity (GHSV) (Medved et al., 2021),
- the composition of the feed gas to the reactor and the nature of its components such as CO₂, CO, N₂ and H₂,
- the operating pressure and temperature,
- a possible recirculation stream, as well as
- the amount of hydrogen required for the methanation reactions to take place expressed as σ_{H_2} (ratio of molar hydrogen flow compared to molar flows of CO and CO₂ (Medved et al., 2021)).

In addition, the parameters might be varied instantly as impulses, in steps or ramps, or changed gradually with a certain slope in increase or decrease. Furthermore, the periodicity is of importance, describing how consistent the dynamics are occurring, as well as the cycle period, which might reach from seconds to hours or even days.

The list of publications in dynamic methanation is long and still increasing, especially for modelling and simulation (Güttel, 2013; Rönisch et al., 2014, 2015; Kreitz et al., 2019b; Currie et al., 2018; Schneider et al., 2016). Nevertheless, realistic industrial applications are yet to be defined, respectively verified for relevance. Given the case of the steel making industry, the dynamic parameters for methanation reduce to only one realistic scenario, which is outlined within this work and investigated through an experimental campaign. The introduced definition is based on the analysis of several years of real-time operations data which was made available by an integrated steel plant in Austria. The data revealed, that among the (theoretically) possible cases listed in the literature, the only real application-based scenario is characterised by a variation in the total volumetric flow rate, where the available hydrogen defines the amount of process gas fed as educt for the methanation. This is a result of the following process boundaries given in the steelmaking process: Although the produced gases from the blast furnace and converter vary significantly in amount and gas composition

Table 2

Application oriented scenario for dynamic methanation in integrated steelworks (dynamic parameters labelled with *).

Parameter/Mode	Target: 100% CO _x conversion
Gas composition	Constant for BFG, BOFG and COG due to gasometers
Pressure	Constant for all gases downstream of gasometers at 4 bar _{abs} (current pressure level for NG lines)
Temperature	For by-product gases: constant For methanation: to be actively controlled to achieve targeted CO _x conversion
*H ₂ amount (incl. excess)	Varying depending on price of electricity (assumption: 5–25% variations in the range of minutes/hours)
Volume flow of process gas	Constant for all gases due to gasometers, for syntheses required amount of BFG and BOFG is available consistently
* Total volume flow/ GHSV	Varying due to the variations in the available hydrogen and H ₂ -excess rate to be kept constant at 5%
Recirculation stream	Only required if favourable for the methanation setup used
* Transient mode	Steps, ramps, slopes Periodic and non-periodic Cycle periods in minutes and hours

(± 50,000 Nm³/h within a range of minutes for BFG) (voestalpine Stahl GmbH, 2022; Wolf-Zoellner et al., 2020), the existing gasometers allow for constant operation of a methanation plant due to their high buffering capacity (100,000 m³ for BFG and 80,000 m³ for BOFG) (Bürgler and Rummer, 2019). As a methanation plant would always be operated downstream of such existing gas tanks, any dynamics in the availability of the by-product gases are buffered and taken out of the process. COG on the other hand is not readily available for a different purpose than the current one, where it is fully integrated in the energy network of an integrated steelworks (Wolf-Zoellner et al., 2021). Therefore, the focus needs to be on the usage of BFG and BOFG, with their very high amount of CO₂, CO and N₂. Finally, the temperature of the available by-product gases as well as the operating pressure remain constant throughout the whole system. This is 20 °C and 55 mbar overpressure for BFG, and 70 °C and 180 mbar for BOFG. With respect to Fig. 1, only two dynamic parameters remain: a possible recirculation stream for active temperature control of the methanation reactors, as well as the overall availability, respectively amount of hydrogen that is required for running the methane synthesis. The latter one is certainly the most relevant parameter for a dynamically driven methanation unit, because, given the fluctuations in the price of electricity for the base and peak load, an installed electrolysis unit must be driven economically. Especially when addressing the operating reserve on the electricity stock market, short term price fluctuations within a range of 5–15 min are possible. Without hydrogen tanks installed, which is expensive and energy consuming, this adds a highly dynamic parameter to the system. The varying hydrogen availability consequently drives the amount of process gas which can be synthesized to SNG, resulting in a dynamic total volume flow, respectively catalyst load as GHSV, for the methanation unit to process.

The target of the Austrian steelmaking plant operator for methanation is to produce a maximum amount of SNG in-plant by converting the produced CO₂ and CO into methane and steam. This subsequently limits the amount of CO₂ that is released to the environment as well as the costs for buying any required natural gas from the external gas grid provider. In addition, the quality of the output stream given by the steel plant operator is that almost no CO₂ and CO should be included anymore, which means full CO_x conversion (Wolf-Zoellner et al., 2021) in the end. The required hydrogen for the synthesis is to be made available by the plant-internal proton-exchange membrane (PEM) electrolyser, driven economically depending on the price of electricity for the operating reserve. Consequently, the amount of available hydrogen will vary permanently, but the surplus to reaction stoichiometry shall be kept between 4 and 5% constantly, in order to achieve the anticipated full methane yield (Medved et al., 2021). Therefore, the dynamic behaviour of the whole system is based on the varying total volume flow as a

Fig. 2. Basic flow sheet of lab-scaled methanation plant.

Table 3
Properties of bulk catalyst Meth 134®.

Parameter	Specification
Catalyst support structure	Aluminium Oxide
Catalytically active material	Nickel
Catalyst composition	Alumina (72.2 wt.%), Calcium Oxide (5.6 wt.%), Nickel (22.2 wt.%), Sulphur (<0.05 wt.-%)
Catalyst form/shape	Spheric
Catalyst diameter	3–6 mm
Catalyst bed porosity	38.9%
Catalyst particle porosity	67.0%
Average crush strength	>68.0 N
Catalyst density	0.9 kg/L

combination of process gas (BFG or BOFG) and hydrogen. Ramps of input gas power adjustments in a range of 5–25% compared to the starting value are to be expected with a duration of 5–30 min until the next ramp up or down can happen. Nevertheless, steps and slopes for increases and decreases as well as non-periodic changes up to hours are also possible.

Table 2 summarises the real application-based scenario for a dynamic methanation case in an integrated steelworks which is defined as part of this work. A further objective is the experimental investigation of the behaviour of such a dynamic operating scenario on the methanation reaction and the catalyst in use. Especially, the effect of highly dynamic changes in syngas input power on the operation and temperature profile of a multi-staged reactor setup is to be investigated. The experimental campaign should ultimately aid in the generation of a profound database, supporting the erection of an upscaled methanation unit in an Austrian steel plant.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Experimental setup

The experimental setup used throughout this work is described by Wolf-Zoellner et al. (2021) in detail. A basic flow sheet of the test rig is shown in Fig. 2. It consists of three cylindrical reactors (R1–R3) with an inner diameter of 80 mm and a length of 300 mm. The reactors can be operated in series or individually and they are either filled with commercial Nickel (Ni)-based bulk catalyst (Meth 134®, specification see Table 3) or with wash-coated honeycomb monoliths (Biegger et al., 2018). Per reactor a volume of 0.25 L over a length of 50 mm is covered with catalyst, and the remaining part is filled with inert stoneware balls. The plant is designed to cover the following operating ranges for methanation of gases from integrated steelworks:

- Volume flow: 0.3–3.0 Nm³/h (5.0–50.0 NL/min)
- GHSV: 1200–12,000 h⁻¹
- Operating pressure: 1–20 bar_(abs)

Fig. 3. Schematic of one reactor with location of multi-thermoelement and catalyst section.

- Maximum reactor temperature: 700 °C

Prior to entering a reactor, the gas stream is guided through a gas mixing station equipped with copper oxide impregnated activated carbon for gas cleaning. Then, it is tempered to temperatures above 200 °C

Table 4
Gas composition of synthetic steelworks gases per gas type.

Gas component	BFG (vol.-% dry)	BOFG (vol.-% dry)
N ₂	48.27	27.59
O ₂	0.00	0.00
CO ₂	23.05	20.01
CO	24.93	51.83
CH ₄	0.00	0.00
H ₂	3.72	0.57
Σ C _n H _m	0.00	0.00

while streaming through heating tubes (W1–W3). Additionally, to reach and keep the required catalyst temperature of 260 °C prior to the methanation synthesis, the reactors are equipped with infrared panels on the outer walls. The heating system is also used to heat the second and third reactor during operation in order to prevent them from cooling down. Once the final product stream leaves the third reactor, it is cooled and guided through a condensate separator before it is combusted in a flare. There is no condensate separation between the reactors R1 and R2 as well as R2 and R3 in place. In total, the plant is equipped with a gas sampling station (QIR) allowing the inlet as well as the product stream after each reactor stage to be analysed for its gas composition. It consists of an infrared photometer URAS 26 (for CO, CO₂, CH₄) and a thermal conductivity analyser CALDOS 27 (for H₂). The sensors are calibrated once a week to keep a maximum deviation of ≤1% per gas component. Furthermore, multi-thermocouples are built into each reactor, enabling the measurement of an axial temperature profile along the catalyst section, as well as directly below and above the catalyst bed. Fig. 3 shows a schematic of the reactor indicating the positions of the catalyst as well as the temperature measurement points (TI) 22 mm eccentric from the reactor middle axis.

2.2. Experimental method & procedure

For the experiments conducted in this work, synthetic gas mixtures were used, matching the gas compositions given in Table 4. These values represent average compositions of real blast furnace and converter gases as they accumulate in an integrated steelworks (voestalpine Stahl GmbH Pr ü ftechnik & Analytik, 2019). Furthermore, the commercial bulk catalyst Meth 134® was used for all three reactors.

Table 5 summarises the operating parameters established and varied

Table 5
Overview of dynamic experiments performed with test rig setup.

#	Experiment	Dynamics	Gas type	Cycle time [min]	GHSV [h ⁻¹]	Flow rate [NL/min]	Reactor inlet temperature (at catalyst section) [°C]	ΔP _{syngas} [%]	σ _{H₂} [-]	p [bar _{abs}]
A	Parameter variation (full combinatoric of all parameters executed)	Jumps Impulses Ramps	BFG BOFG	30	2000	8.4	120–260	±50	1.00–1.10 (in steps of 0.01)	1
					3000	12.6	2			
					4000	16.8	4			
					5000	20.9	5			
					6000	25.1	7.5			
B	Application-based GHSV variation with constant H ₂ excess rate	Jumps	BFG BOFG	5	4000–5000 – 3500 –	16.8–20.9 – 14.7 –	240–260	±25	1.05	4
					– 4500–4000	– 18.9–16.8				
					4000–3000 – 5000 –	16.8–12.6 – 20.9 –				
					– 3500–4500 – 4000	– 14.7–18.9 – 16.8				
					4000–3600 – 4000	16.8–15.1 – 16.8				
C	Simulation-based scenario for converter including highly dynamic electricity prices for electrolyser (Dettori et al., 2021; Matino et al., 2019; Hauser et al., 2022)	Jumps Ramps	BOFG	1–120	3500–6000	14.7–25.1	230–240	Δ = 64%	1.04	4

throughout the experimental campaign. The dynamic experiments in section #A were performed to establish a full understanding of the behaviour of the methanation test rig under dynamically changing input parameters, with the targets to study the buffering capacity of the reactors, to evaluate if certain gas components are leading ahead of others (Wolf-Zoellner et al., 2019a), as well as to measure the effect of the large share of N₂ injected as part of the steelworks gases (Medved, 2020). Synthetic BFG and BOFG mixtures with a surplus of hydrogen from 1.0 to 1.1 were upgraded at pressure ratings between 1 and 10 bar_{abs}. The catalyst loading stayed between 2000 and 6000 h⁻¹ which represents a change in syngas power of ±50%. Dynamic changes were executed as jumps, impulses, as well as with slopes/ramps over a cycle duration of 30 min (Wolf-Zoellner et al., 2019b). The experiments revealed that high pressures result in the expected higher CO_x conversion rates, whereas an increase in total volume flow inhibits the conversion due to the shortened residence time. The variation also confirmed that full CO_x conversion can already be achieved with 4–5% in H₂ excess using the three-staged methanation setup operated within an optimum GHSV range (3000–5000 h⁻¹) at 4 bar_{abs}. Furthermore, the comparison of steady state and dynamic experiments by jumps showed that the achievable methane yield and hydrogen conversion do not differ from each other. The cycle time and the jump width had no impact on the final gas composition. However, the changes caused jumps of the hot-spot temperature. It was found that the variation in the volumetric flow rate had a larger impact on the temperature profiles and the overall temperature level of the first reactor stage than the variation of the stoichiometric ratio. All these effects have been similar for BFG as well as for BOFG as feed gases. Regarding the degradation of the used catalysts, no decline in the catalytic activity was observed. There was no shift of the temperature profiles into the reactor, as it would be expected when catalyst deactivation occurred beginning at the reactor inlet.

The dynamic experiments in section #B represent the application-based scenario from Table 2 with a varying hydrogen availability within time periods of 5–45 min. Prior to any dynamics, steady state conditions for all three reactors with a GHSV of 4000 h⁻¹ and a σ_{H₂} of 1.05 at 4 bar_{abs} operating pressure were established. After about 2 h of steady state methanation, the amount of process gas used for the methanation synthesis was reduced or increased, keeping a constant H₂-excess rate of 5%. During these changes, the catalyst load stayed between 3000 and 5000 h⁻¹, which represents variations in syngas power of ±25%.

Fig. 4. Time-based data for dynamic experiment with BFG (4 bar, 5% H₂-excess), representative GHSV variation from experiment section #B, experiment duration: 2.83 h, product gas composition behind R3 in vol.-% dry, CO_x conversion in %, pressure in bar_{abs} and GHSV in 10³ h⁻¹, 12 representative points highlighted with black dots.

Fig. 5. Dynamic experiment with BFG at 4 bar and 5% H₂-excess; left: CO_x conversion and reactor temperatures in R3 for each representative measurement point, values in % and °C, GHSV variation from section #B in h⁻¹, colour variation for each GHSV step change established; right: product gas composition and mean reactor temperatures in R3 for each representative measurement point, values in vol.-% dry and °C, GHSV variation from section #B in h⁻¹.

For the design of the experiments listed in section #C the theoretical studies of Dettori et al. (2021), Matino et al. (2019) and Hauser et al. (2022) were used as input, who modelled a steel plant using deep learning and neuronal network-based approaches, with the target to forecast the off-gas production and consumption in a basic oxygen furnace. The authors provide a simulated dataset for volume flow of BOFG as well as hydrogen in surplus ($\sigma_{H_2} = 1.04$). It includes jumps and ramps in GHSV with changes in syngas input power up to 64% in the range of one to 120 min.

3. Experimental results and discussion

The real-time measurement values for a representative experiment with BFG out of section #B (Table 5) are shown in Fig. 4. After an initial steady-state phase of 35 min at 4000 h⁻¹, the GHSV (orange curve) was varied within a range of 5000 and 3000 h⁻¹ in steps of 500 h⁻¹. These step changes were executed every 5, 10 and 15 min over a period of 70 min. Afterwards, the initial GHSV of 4000 h⁻¹ was established again for 45 min prior to a drop to 3000 h⁻¹ where it remained for 20 min until the end of the experiment. The blue curve represents the calculated CO_x conversion which stayed very close at the maximum possible value varying between 99.0 and 100% even though the total volume flow rate

varied within a range of ±25%. The operating pressure (purple curve) remained constant at 4.1 bar_{abs} (±0.1 bar_{abs}).

Fig. 5 (left) gives an overview on the achieved CO_x conversion rates at twelve representative measurement points, one for each step change. These points are also marked with black dots in Fig. 4 (#1 - #12). As the CO_x conversion remained stable throughout the duration of the experiment, logically also the amount of SNG and hydrogen present in the product stream was constant. Any remaining CO was fully converted, but nevertheless a small portion of CO₂ remained in the product gas (~0.3 vol.-% in average). Noticeable is the link between CO_x conversion and GHSV, which increased with the lower GHSVs at 3000 h⁻¹ and decreased with the ones at 5000 h⁻¹. Also, the mean reactor temperature in R3 showed an immediate response with the step changes executed, increasing for lower GHSVs, and decreasing for higher ones. This is a result of the longer residence time of the reactive gases within the reactor, allowing more CH₄ to be produced. Nevertheless, the mean temperature varied only between 276.5 and 285.3 °C inside the third reactor, as well as between 304.0 and 311.4 °C at the top of the catalyst bed. This temperature determines the overall performance of the methanation reaction in the used setup, because the exothermic equilibrium reaction is not kinetically, but thermodynamically limited.

The detailed product gas composition for the representative

Fig. 6. Reactor temperatures in R1, R2 and R3 during dynamic experiments with BFG at 4 bar and 5% H₂-excess.

measurement points in time is given in Fig. 5 at the right. Due to the high share of nitrogen in the feed gas and the volume reducing methanation reaction, the composition of the product included up to 43.0 vol.-% dry of nitrogen. Furthermore, the product consisted of up to 12.0 vol.-% dry of unreacted hydrogen for high flow rates and 10.6 vol.-% dry for lower ones. Although the input gas power varied up to 25% around the established starting value of GHSV = 4000 h⁻¹, only small differences in the final product gas composition are noticeable ($\pm 0.5\%$ for N₂, $\pm 0.7\%$ for H₂, $\pm 0.9\%$ for CH₄, $\pm 0.1\%$ for CO₂, all within deviation range of the used gas analytics). However, the temperature profile in the first reactor clearly shows a response to the step changes executed. As Fig. 6 indicates, the hotspot temperature at TI4 (see Fig. 3) in R1 varied between 569.2 and 500.8 °C and followed the variations in GHSV instantly. Prior to these adjustments, the temperatures could stabilise at repeatable values for the same GHSVs (± 2 °C range). For the reactors R2 and

especially R3 a different temperature behaviour was observed. Firstly, both reactors required to be heated with the installed infrared panels to prevent them from cooling down. This is simply due to the fact, that reactor R1 took most of the methanation load and left only a small amount of reactive gases (CO and CO₂) for the other two reactors to synthesise with hydrogen to methane and steam. Consequently, the heat losses for these two reactors were higher than the exothermic reaction heat produced in R2 and R3. The temperature profile for R2 shows that the temperature has not reached a steady-state condition prior to the next step change in GHSV. Nevertheless, the temperatures at the individual measurement points showed a clear response to the executed variations. For R3 on the other hand, no direct response could be observed as the temperatures stayed at the same level during the whole duration of the experiment. The small variations every 5 min are a response of the control system automatically adjusting the heating capacity of the infrared panels. This results in the conclusion, that the operation of the third reactor and the resulting temperature at the top of the catalyst bed drives the overall output of the setup in terms of CO_x conversion. Furthermore, the serial connection of the three polytropic reactors results in a buffering effect, taking out any of the dynamics executed on the input stream.

Similar dynamic cycles were also performed with converter gas and a hydrogen surplus of 5%. Starting at 4000 h⁻¹, the GHSV (orange curve in Fig. 7) varied in steps of 500 h⁻¹ between 3000 and 5000 h⁻¹ with cycle times of 10 min each. As for BFG, the CO_x conversion stayed very close to the maximum possible value with variations between 98.8 and 99.9% (blue curve in Fig. 7).

For this experiment eleven representative points in time (#13 - #23) are selected. The individual CO_x conversion rates (Fig. 8 left) and product gas compositions (Fig. 8 right) at these measurements show a very constant behaviour again, although the input gas power varied within a $\pm 25\%$ range around the starting value. The operating pressure was again set to 4.1 bar_{abs}. The remaining CO₂ in the product gas was slightly higher for BOFG compared to BFG averaging at ~ 0.5 vol.-% dry. Due to the far lower share of nitrogen in the converter gas, which includes up to 72% of convertible CO₂ and CO, the product gas had consequently higher shares of SNG (61.8–64.5 vol.-% dry). The share of nitrogen varied between 20.4 and 21.6 vol.-% dry. Consequently, also the mean reactor temperature as well as the temperature at the top of the catalyst bulk was higher compared to the case for BFG. The temperatures for R3 varied between 328.0 and 339.1 °C as well as 302.5 and 315.2 °C, respectively. With the last step change to 4000 h⁻¹ the temperature inside the reactor could be decreased to 313.7 °C in average, resulting in the highest CO_x conversion rate (99.9%) that was achieved during the

Fig. 7. Time-based data for dynamic experiment with BOFG (4 bar, 5% H₂-excess), representative GHSV variation from experiment section #B, experiment duration: 2.0 h, product gas composition behind R3 in vol.-% dry, CO_x conversion in %, pressure in bar_{abs} and GHSV in 10³ h⁻¹, 11 representative points highlighted with black dots.

Fig. 8. Dynamic experiment with BOFG at 4 bar and 5% H₂-excess; left: CO_x conversion and reactor temperatures in R3 for each representative measurement point, values in % and °C, GHSV variation from section #B in h⁻¹; colour variation for each GHSV step change established; right: product gas composition and mean reactor temperatures in R3 for each representative measurement point, values in vol.-% dry and °C, GHSV variation from section #B in h⁻¹.

Fig. 9. Reactor temperatures in R1, R2 and R3 during dynamic experiments with BOFG at 4 bar and 5% H₂-excess.

experiment. These results consistently confirm that the methanation reaction is thermodynamically limited in the used lab setup as the conversion rates are lower with higher reactor temperatures at the outlet. Furthermore, the reaction rate easily compensates the performed fluctuations in input gas power, i.e., changes in GHSV. After any set of experiments, the temperature profile along the catalyst bed was examined, and no significant deactivation of the used catalyst could be observed for the dynamic operating cases performed.

As with BFG, active control of the temperatures inside the reactors R2 and R3 is essential in order to maintain a stable and high CO_x conversion at the product side. Without heating these two reactors, the gas streams entering them would cool down the catalyst section below 200 °C within minutes and result in the formation of poisonous Nickel carbonyl. In contrast to the BFG experiments, the temperatures in R1 and R2 were generally higher by ~50 °C, which is a result of the higher share of CO and CO₂ in the converter gases (Fig. 9). Consequently, also

Fig. 10. Gas quality specification according to ÖVGW G B210 and achieved methanation product gas qualities for BFG and BOFG as feed gases, values in kWh/Nm³.

the temperature trend following the GHSV variations is stronger compared to the one for BFG. The temperature profile in R3 on the other hand is very similar to the one reported for BFG, as the complete catalyst section remained between 250 and 350 °C.

From the standpoint of a steelworks plant operator, the gas streams produced for the presented application-based methanation scenarios require further gas upgrading to substitute the need of purchasing natural gas from the external gas grid. With a Wobbe-Index W_s of about ~6.6 kWh/Nm³ and a higher calorific value H_s of ~5.4 kWh/Nm³ for the BFG synthesized gas, respectively ~10.0 and ~7.5 kWh/Nm³ for BOFG, the specifications of the Austrian regulations ÖVGW G B210 (Österreichische Vereinigung für das Gas, 2021) are missed by far (Fig. 10). This is mainly caused by the high share of nitrogen which is only passed through the system without taking part in the synthesis reactions. The presence of unreacted hydrogen in the product gas is the second factor reducing the Wobbe-Index and calorific value. Consequently, the produced gas streams require further treatment prior to injection into the natural gas grid. From a process technology point of view, the extraction of methane through liquification and supply as liquified natural gas (LNG) is costly. Covering parts of the internal demand of natural gas with self-produced methane seems to be the most reasonable option for a steelworks' operator, where it can also be used as

Fig. 11. Time-based data for dynamic experiment with BOFG (4 bar, 4% H₂-excess), representative GHSV variation from experiment section #C, experiment duration: 10 h, product gas composition behind R3 in vol.-% dry, CO_x conversion in % and GHSV in 10³ h⁻¹, 18 representative points highlighted with black dots.

Fig. 12. Dynamic experiment with BOFG at 4 bar and 5% H₂-excess; left: product gas composition and maximum reactor temperatures of R1, R2 and R3 for each representative measurement point, values in vol.-% dry and °C, GHSV variation from section #C in h⁻¹; right: CO_x conversion and GHSV for each representative measurement point, values in % and h⁻¹, GHSV variation from section #C in h⁻¹.

lean gas for plant internal firing and auxiliary operations.

The simulation-based experiment from section #C in Table 5 are characterised by converter gas only, as well as a hydrogen surplus of 4% compared to reaction stoichiometry. Fig. 11 shows the product gas composition, the input volume flow expressed as GHSV as well as the achieved CO_x conversion for 10 h of methanation. After a conditioning phase of 60 min, assuring that the catalyst inside the reactors is heated up according to the design specifications given by the manufacturer, the total volume flow of BOFG and hydrogen varied between 15 and 20 NL/min ($\hat{=}$ 3500–4800 h⁻¹ GHSV) in a range of \pm 20 min. The flow rate was characterised by very smooth slopes in increase and decrease without any imminent changes such as jumps or impulses. After a period of 4 h, a steady increase in GHSV occurred over the next 2 h up to a maximum flow rate of \sim 24 NL/min ($\hat{=}$ 5740 h⁻¹ GHSV). During the following 3 h the total volume flow remained at this elevated level varying between 21 and 24 NL/min. Again, only smooth slopes with rates of 0.25 NL/min up and down were transferred to the plant control system. Afterwards, the flow rate was decreased to 19.7 NL/min ($\hat{=}$ 4700 h⁻¹ GHSV) where it stayed constant for about 1 h prior to the shutting down phase of 60 min. During the experiment the operating pressure stayed at 4 bar_{abs} constantly.

The periodic changes during the first half of the experiment were within a range of \pm 20% in gas input power. In total, six cycles were executed with an average duration of 44 min. The gain in total volume flow up to the elevated level of 24 NL/min during the second half

represents a percentual increase of 56%. Although such high variations in gas input power have been performed, the product gas composition measured downstream of the third reactor (R3) stayed constant again, with only small variations within 4 vol.-% depending on the gas component. The left chart in Fig. 12 gives an overview on the detailed gas composition for 18 dedicated measurement points highlighted with black dots in Fig. 11. Fig. 12 on the right shows the CO_x conversion rates for the very same points in time. During the first half, hydrogen varied between 66.8 and 69.5 vol.-%, and methane concentration ranges between 11.6 and 13.9 vol.-%. The share for CO₂ remained at a very low level of about 0.5 vol.-%. As no CO could be detected in the product gas, the CO_x conversion constantly remained above 99%, even though the mentioned high variations in gas input power were executed. In total, a range of 64% of syngas input power was covered. With the increase in GHSV during the second half and the resulting shorter residence time, the performance of the methanation unit dropped slightly. A remaining share of hydrogen of about 15 vol.-%, and for methane of 64 vol.-% was observed. CO₂ increased to about 1.2 vol.-% resulting in CO_x conversion rates around 98% in average. Fig. 13 indicates that the temperature profile in R1 followed the dynamic changes in GHSV varying between 560 and 660 °C. Reactor two showed a similar behaviour when following the GHSV changes but with generally smoother responses. The trend towards lower temperatures is a result of the decreased heating of R2 in order to achieve an optimal temperature level for this reactor. After 5 h of operation the heating stabilised, and with the large increase

Fig. 13. Reactor temperatures in R1, R2 and R3 during dynamic experiments with BOFG at 4 bar and 5% H₂-excess.

in GHSV also the temperature level increased again. Furthermore, the heating of R3 had to be increased after 8 h of operation to prevent the reactor from cooling down below 200 °C. Unfortunately, the power of the rather slow responding heating system with infrared panels was increased too much, which resulted in temperatures up to 345 °C at the top of the catalyst section instead of only 320 °C. Consequently, the conversion rates further decreased even though the GHSV was decreased again close to the end of the experiment. This behaviour confirms the conclusions already drawn for the dynamic experiments with BFG and BOFG. A fast responding and automated temperature control system for the second and especially third reactor is essential in order to assure a constant gas composition and maximum CO_x conversion for the product stream. This requirement increases with the magnitude of dynamic changes in the syngas input power of the educt stream.

4. Summary and conclusions

The catalytic methanation is still frequently researched as it is seen as an important bridging technology for the overall target to reduce the global emissions of CO₂. Dynamic operation of such a system is currently mainly addressed through modelling and simulation. Especially the steel industry is exploring possible solutions to reduce their overall CO₂ emissions and contribute to a more sustainable steel production as well as to climate protection by reduction of greenhouse gas emissions. Consequently, first methanation units are being designed and erected to upgrade the steel plant's by-product gases to SNG. In this work, a real application-based scenario of dynamic methanation in an integrated steelworks has been experimentally investigated with the target to substitute the steel mills demand of any externally sourced natural gas. However, the availability of gasometers and process boundaries reveal that a methanation unit would mainly be operated at steady state. In case the operator of a steel plant is going to drive the installed electrolyzer highly economically based on the operating reserve, dynamics for the methanation synthesis stems exclusively from the amount of hydrogen produced. Consequently, the theoretically possible dynamic operation cases reduce to only one real application-based scenario: the

variation in total volumetric flow rate, where the amount of process gas as feed gas to the methanation is adjusted based on the availability of hydrogen.

Experiments with a three-stage methanation setup in lab-scale showed that a constant hydrogen surplus of 4–5% to reaction stoichiometry is required to meet the target of full CO_x conversion. It was furthermore possible to achieve very stable product gas compositions, even though high changes in syngas input power up to 64% in the range of one to 120 min were executed. An analysis of the temporal temperature profiles in the three reactors revealed that only the first reactor in the series is affected by significant temperature changes due to the dynamic operation. Higher gas flows (GHSV) result in an increased release of reaction heat and consequently in an increase of reactor temperature. However, the second and particularly the third reactor show an almost constant temperature profile. Both reactors need to be externally heated for balancing the heat losses and for keeping the reactors at an operating temperature above 200 °C due to the low released reaction heat. Therefore, an optimal temperature control of the second and especially third reactor is essential to assure the specified quality of the product gas. Obviously, dynamic changes in feed gas flow rate can be compensated by three polytropic reactors in series. The product gas composition depends only on the reactor temperature of the last reactor and is determined by the thermodynamic equilibrium.

Furthermore, the dynamic variations did not result in any additional catalyst deactivation throughout the whole experimental campaign. The high share of nitrogen in the by-product gases and consequently also in the methanation product gases require further gas upgrading in case the SNG is to be injected in the natural gas grid. Optionally, the produced SNG can also be used for firing and auxiliary operations steel plant-internally. The experiments further revealed that the defined application-based dynamic scenario can be mapped with a methanation system. Consequently, the installation of hydrogen tanks, just to take any dynamics out of the system to achieve a steady state methanation, is not required.

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Philipp Wolf-Zoellner: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Visualization. **Markus Lehner:** Conceptualization, Validation, Investigation, Supervision, Writing - review & editing. **Nina Kieberger:** Validation, Supervision, Writing - review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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